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Gelatin-Assisted Defect Engineering in LaCoO₃ and Its Impact on Oxygen Electrocatalysis

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Nanocrystalline LaCoO₃ materials prepared by a spray-freeze freeze-drying approach in the presence of various amounts of gelatine were tested in oxygen electrocatalysis in alkaline media. Gelatine in the reaction mixture affects the distribution of the oxygen vacancies as well as formation of Ruddlesen–Popper (RP) defects within nanocrystals. Materials prepared at low gelatine concentration ($c \cong 1.5 \text{ g l}^{-1}$) tend to locate the oxygen vacancies at the domain boundaries while increasing gelatine concentration promotes a larger formation of superstructure, where the oxygen vacancies get ordered along the (100) pseudocubic direction in the crystal. The ordered vacancies and RP faults are primary sites of exfoliation in acid media, steering the electrocatalytic behavior of the prepared materials in both oxygen evolution and oxygen reduction. Exfoliation significantly promotes the oxygen evolution reaction activity via a new surface formation increasing the presence of Co (III)/Co (IV) species at the surface which are responsible for oxygen evolution. On the other hand, exfoliation also leads to a change of the oxygen reduction reaction mechanism, promoting four-electron reduction over the two-electron peroxide formation. This behavior can be attributed to a change of reactivity of the exfoliated surfaces, which apparently adsorb peroxo intermediates more strongly than as prepared materials.

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The intermittent nature of renewable energy sources replacing conventional fossil energy sources increases the demand for energy storage systems.^{1,2} One of the prospective means for long term energy storage is the conversion of electric energy into energy of chemical bonds.³ One of the possible environmentally friendly solutions is a hydrogen-based energy concept combining water electrolyzers with hydrogen fuel cells.^{4,5} A significant cost reduction in this concept can be achieved by implementing so called reversible fuel cells or unitized regenerative fuel cells (URFC) integrating both technologies into one device.⁶ Such devices switch between both modes, are highly compact and need less material. Their use is valuable in the sectors restricted by area and mass, such as space, aviation, and transportation.^{7,8} The effective performance of the URFCs depends on the quality and durability of membranes,⁹ activity and the long-term stability of bifunctional electrocatalysts,¹⁰ the function of which is to catalyze hydrogen evolution/oxidation reaction (HER/HOR) at one side and oxygen evolution/reduction (OER/ORR) at the other side. The efficiency of such devices is, however, limited by sluggish kinetics of oxygen reactions resulting in high overpotential leading to energy losses.^{11–13} This obstacle should be overcome by tailoring electrode catalyst materials which have to be stable over a wide potential range in oxidative and reductive conditions at extreme pH.¹⁴ One of the prospective materials which could replace the noble metals in these applications may be nanostructured transition metal oxides,^{10,15} namely of perovskite structure.

Perovskites (ABO₃) are the promising class of catalysts for oxygen electrocatalysis in terms of cost, easy synthesis, and flexibility in tuning the properties by chemical modification in the B-site.¹⁶ The A position in perovskite structure is usually occupied by an alkaline earth- or a rare-earth metal while the B site accommodates transition metal cations carrying most of the reactivity. This structural arrangement attracted a lot of attention due to its flexibility in modifying chemical properties as was shown namely in OER/ORR electrocatalysis.^{17,18} LaCoO₃ stands out among ABO₃ type of perovskites as an excellent candidate for a bifunctional catalysis due to the large ionic radius of La in the A site and

moderate Co–O bond strength in the B site leading to a convenient O–Co–O arrangement approaching the value predicted for efficient bifunctional catalysts theoretically.¹⁹ Although URFC electrodes are supposed to support both oxidation and reduction, one may not expect that both reactions will be catalyzed by the same active sites. This is particularly the case for the oxygen electrode in which an employment of the same sites in forward and backward reactions is hindered by the interdependence of OH and OOH binding at the surface.^{13,17}

Due to a clear demand to confine the oxygen evolution and reduction to different surface sites one may turn to perovskites aiming at exploring multiple valences, which may act as electron donors and acceptors, namely if one aims for catalysis in alkaline media. In this paper, we report the electrocatalytic behavior of LaCoO₃ materials with respect to potential use in URFC. The LaCoO₃ based materials were prepared using the spray-freeze freeze-drying approach with the addition of different amounts of structure-directing gelatine to introduce the structural defects into the nanocrystals. Additionally, an effect of post-synthesis exfoliation in both oxygen evolution and reduction will be described to demonstrate the role of the defects in both catalytic processes.

Experimental

Materials and chemicals.—The chemicals for the synthesis of LaCoO₃: lanthanum acetate hydrate- La(OOCCH₃)₃ · x H₂O (Sigma-Aldrich, 99.9%), cobalt nitrate hexahydrate (Aldrich, 99%), acetic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, ≥99%), Gelatine (Penta chemicals, p.a.), and milli-Q quality de-ionized (DI) water were used as received. Gelatine powder was used in proportions varying from a concentration of 0.3 g l⁻¹ to 7.5 g l⁻¹. Potassium hydroxide (KOH) pellets (Penta Chemicals, p.a.) were used for electrolyte preparation. Isopropyl alcohol (IPA; Lach:ner, ≥99.96%) was used in ink preparation.

Syntheses.—The LaCoO₃ samples were prepared by spray-freeze freeze-drying (SFFD) approach.^{20–25} The main advantage of the applied approach is its ability to achieve an atomary mixing of components of a complex oxide at low temperature which can be

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converted to its final structure by a mild annealing.²⁶ In this manner one can kinetically stabilize phases otherwise unavailable due to their metastable nature. In our particular case the metal precursor solutions of lanthanum acetate and cobalt nitrate were prepared by dissolving the corresponding metal salts in DI water to reach a metal ratio of 1:1. The total metal concentration of the prepared solutions was kept at 10 mM in all syntheses. The water content in the lanthanum acetate hydrate x was assumed to be 1.3 based on previous studies.²¹ The stock solution of metal precursors was complemented by the addition of a variable amount of gelatine to reach the gelatine concentration between 0.3 and 7.5 g l⁻¹. The solutions were heated at 80 °C to allow complete dissolution of the gelatine, stirred for half an hour and left to cool off before the spray-freezing step. Cooled solutions were sprayed into 1 l of liquid nitrogen to form the ice-based precursors. The frozen solvent from ice based precursors was removed in the freeze-drying step at reduced pressure (1 Pa) using FreeZone Triad Freeze-Dry system 7400030 (Labconco). The following a temperature protocol was employed in the freeze drying procedure: -30 °C during the evacuation of the cooling chamber, followed by a gradual temperature increase (-30 °C (2 h), -25 °C (5 h), -20 °C (4 h), -15 °C (6 h), +30 °C (4 h)). The dried, foam-like precursor was carefully removed from the freeze-dryer and annealed at 700 °C for 2 h in air. The sequence of the spray freeze freeze drying synthesis is summarized in the Scheme 1.

Thermal behaviour of the dried precursor was characterized using thermogravimeter STA449F1 (Netzsch). The thermogravimetric and behavior was studied on 10–20 mg of the sample, which was placed inside an alumina crucible and heated in a temperature range from 40 °C to 800 °C in simulated air (a combination of argon and oxygen (Ar: O₂) with a flow rate of 24 ml min⁻¹ and 6 ml min⁻¹ respectively).

Characterization.—The crystallinity and phase purity of the samples were analyzed with a powder X-ray diffraction (XRD). The diffraction patterns were recorded using a Rigaku Miniflex 600 powder X-ray diffractometer with Cu K α radiation operating at 30 kV and 10 mA. Eight scans were averaged to obtain the data quality needed for Rietveld refinement. Rietveld refinement was performed to determine the unit cell parameters as well as contamination content with the Profex 5.1.0 software package.²⁷ The particle size of the prepared samples was determined by scanning electron micrographs acquired with a Hitachi S4800 scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with a Nanotracer EDX detector (Thermo Electron).

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was carried out on an FEI Tecnai TF20 X-twin microscope operated at 200 kV (FEG, 2.5 Å point resolution) equipped with an EDAX Energy Dispersive X-ray (EDX) detector. The microscope was also used in scanning mode (STEM) with High-Angle Annular Dark Field Detector (HAADF). TEM images and selected-area electron diffraction (SAED) patterns were recorded on a Gatan CCD camera with resolution of 2048×2048 pixels using the Digital Micrograph software package. SAED patterns were evaluated using the Process Diffraction software package.²⁸ The EDX spectra/maps were processed using the FEI TIA software. High resolution TEM (HR-TEM) micrographs were treated by Geometrical Phase Analysis (GPA)²⁹ performed in CrysTBox³⁰ to calculate strain and displacement distribution maps. Powder samples were dispersed in ethanol and the suspension was treated in ultrasound for 5 min. A drop of dilute suspension was placed on a holey-carbon-coated copper grid and allowed to dry by evaporation at ambient temperature.

Electrochemical characterization.—The LaCoO₃ based electrodes for electrochemical characterization were prepared by drop casting catalysts containing inks on glassy carbon substrates. The catalyst containing inks were prepared as described below. An ink increment of 10 μ l was deposited on a polished glassy-carbon

Scheme 1. Schematic representation of the spray freeze freeze drying synthetic procedure.

disk electrode (0.196 cm²) to reach a total catalyst loading of 100 μ g_{cat} cm⁻². The same loading of the catalyst was kept in all measurements. Before ink drop-casting, the glassy carbon electrode was polished to a mirror appearance using 0.05 μ m size alumina suspension in each case.

Ink 1 (without an exfoliating agent).—Homogeneous catalyst ink dispersion was prepared by mixing 5 mg of the catalyst with 2.0 ml of IPA and 0.5 ml of Milli-Q quality water. The catalyst ink suspension was sonicated until a homogeneous solution was formed, and labelled as non-exfoliating ink.

Ink 2 (with exfoliating agent).—The catalyst was exfoliated by adding 0.1 μ mol of acetic acid to Ink 1. After addition, the ink mixture was sonicated for 1 h at a constant temperature of 25 °C. Then the ink was prepared for depositions.

Electrochemical OER measurements.—Electrochemical OER testing of prepared LaCoO₃ phases was performed in a single-compartment three-electrode cell with a rotating disk electrode (RDE) set-up controlled by an Autolab PGSTAT30 potentiostat. A 5 mm glassy carbon electrode was utilized as a working electrode coated with a thin film of catalyst ink. Pt mesh and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) were used as counter and reference electrodes, respectively. All potentials were recalculated and are reported in the reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE) scale by utilizing the equation $E_{RHE} = E_{measured} + 0.059 \cdot \text{pH} + E^{\circ}_{SCE}$, where $E^{\circ}_{SCE} = 0.236$ V at 25 °C. All electrochemical tests were performed in 0.1 M KOH. During the OER experiments, the electrolyte was purged with argon (Ar; Messer, $\geq 99.9\%$) gas for 30 min before measurements. Cyclic voltammetry was performed in the potential range of -0.5 V to 1.7 V vs RHE at a scan rate of 10 mV s⁻¹. Linear scan voltammetry (LSV) was done in the potential range from 1.0 V–1.7 V vs RHE at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹. Tafel slopes were derived from linear scan voltammetry curves recorded in the potential range of 1.1 V–1.8 V at a scan rate of 1 mV s⁻¹. Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) measurements were performed in a frequency range from 15 kHz to 1 kHz with amplitude of 10 mV (peak to peak) to determine the uncompensated resistance of the system.

Electrochemical ORR measurements.—ORR activity was measured utilizing the rotating ring disk electrode (RRDE) set-up equipped with a 5 mm glassy carbon substrate as disk and Pt as ring electrode (Pine instruments). The prepared ink of LaCoO_3 was drop cast on the disk electrode (loading of $100 \mu\text{g}_{\text{cat}} \text{cm}^{-2}$). ORR activity investigations took place in an O_2 -saturated 0.1 M KOH electrolyte. The potential of the disk electrode was scanned within the range from 1.1 V to 0.05 V vs RHE at a rate of 5 mV s^{-1} . The LSV curves were collected at different rotation speeds of 0, 400, 900, 1200, and 1600 rotations per minute (rpm). The potential of the ring was kept at 1.2 V vs RHE during the experiments to probe H_2O_2 formation. The collection factor of the RRDE electrode was 0.37 ± 0.01 . The measurements at 1600 rpm were chosen to compare the ORR activity of all prepared samples.

Results and Discussion

The SFFD synthesis of La–Co–O oxides yields amorphous precursors, which need to be annealed at 700°C to crystallize single phase materials. All prepared LaCoO_3 materials conform to the perovskite structural type. Detailed information on the structure of the prepared LaCoO_3 phases is extracted from the Rietveld refinement of the experimental XRD patterns.

Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) of LaCoO_3 synthesized in the absence of gelatine shows the best convergence to the rhombohedral perovskite structure (R-3c, 167) (Fig. 1a). PXRD patterns of the samples prepared in the presence of different gelatine concentrations are compared in Fig. 1b. The addition of low concentrations of gelatine ($c \leq 1.5 \text{ g l}^{-1}$) supports the formation of apparently single phase nano-crystalline materials similar to those synthesized in the absence of gelatine (0.0 g l^{-1}). The diffraction patterns show no significant difference in the crystal structure attributable to the gelatine presence. Synthesis in the presence of a higher gelatine concentration $c \geq 1.5 \text{ g l}^{-1}$ leads to the formation of secondary crystalline phases. These secondary phases are mostly La-rich oxides: La_2O_3 ³¹ and $\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$ ³² (see Fig. S1). The presence of the secondary La-rich phases is compensated by the formation of small amounts of Co rich phases, most likely Co_3O_4 . The formation of secondary phases in the reaction mixtures containing large gelatine concentrations can be connected with the chemical processes proceeding in the dried precursor during annealing. It may be conceived that organics present in the dried precursor may be ignited in presence of nitrates driving the actual temperature of the precursor

above the stability limit of the ternary phase resulting in formation of lanthanum and cobalt oxides. More detailed analysis of the annealing process along with the TG and DSC data is given in Supporting Information (see Figs. S2 and S3).

The content of secondary phases increases with increasing gelatine content in the whole range of used gelatine concentrations (7.5 g l^{-1}). At the highest gelatine concentration, the La rich phases form approximately 2.5% of the total sample volume with traces of Co-based oxides detected alongside. Hence, the phase composition of synthesized materials changes with the variation of gelatine amount. On the other hand, given the small amount of the secondary phases, their effect on the catalytic activity of the prepared materials can be neglected (see below). The similar can be said of the unburned remnants of organics which amount roughly to 1% of the prepared material mass. The results of full-fledged Rietveld refinement of the diffraction patterns of materials prepared at different gelatine concentrations are given in Table S1 of the Supporting Information. In fact, a similar behavior when the addition of gelatine leads to a formation of secondary phases has been reported for La–Ni–O system.²¹

The addition of gelatine has a pronounced effect on the morphology of synthesized materials as well as on size of their particles. (Fig. 2).

The particles prepared without gelatine (0.0 g l^{-1}) do not have prevailing particle shape, consequently their surface orientation is random. The addition of gelatine leads to a change in the shape and size of the synthesised nanoparticles. The average particle size analysis (Figs. S4 and S5) reveals a decrease in the nanoparticle sizes with increasing concentrations of gelatine. The decrease in the particle size encountered with the addition of gelatine leads also to the emergence of crystals with defined facets. The effect is enhanced for the materials prepared at the concentration of gelatine higher than 1.5 g l^{-1} (see Fig. 2). At high concentrations of 5.0 g l^{-1} and 7.5 g l^{-1} , cube-like nanoparticles predominate in the prepared materials (see Fig. 2a). The overall effect of gelatine content on the particle size of the prepared materials is shown in Fig. 2b.

Although all samples are composed of rhombohedral LaCoO_3 cuboid particles they do not form perfect single crystals. They display rich structure variations on the atomic scale, which were analyzed in detail by FFT and GPA analysis (see Figs. 3, S6 and S7).

HRTEM images of the materials prepared without gelatine show a tweed-like pattern, which confirms a formation of ordered superstructure. This superstructure manifests itself by additional

Figure 1. (a) Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern of lanthanum cobalt oxide sample synthesized without gelatine after Rietveld refinement considering rhombohedral LaCoO_3 (R-3c, No. 167) as main phase with traces of cobalt oxide (b) PXRD patterns of lanthanum cobalt oxide synthesized with different amounts of gelatine (0.0 g l^{-1} to 7.5 g l^{-1}). Additional phases of lanthanum-based contaminants ($\text{La}_2\text{O}_3/\text{La}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$) after the addition of gelatine are marked with asterisks (*) and Co (II, III) oxides are marked with (o).

Figure 2. (a) SEM micrographs and, (b) particle size dependence of LaCoO_3 on gelatine concentration in the reaction mixture. The actual concentration values are shown in figure legend.

diffraction spots with a tripling along $\langle 100 \rangle$ pseudocubic direction in the FFT (see column 3 row a in Fig. 3). The literature ascribes such superstructures to the ordering of oxygen vacancies,^{33,34} charge ordering due to the mixed valence state of Co,³³ and/or spin-orbital ordering.³⁵

Samples prepared in the presence of gelatine in addition to oxygen vacancies also show stacking defects in the structure. The occurrence and distribution of such defects are affected by the concentration of gelatine during synthesis. The defects are, generally, inhomogeneously distributed through the particles and seem

confined to boundaries separating larger single-crystal domains. They show limited, if any, periodicity as exhibited by the continuous streaks in the corresponding FFTs of the HRTEM images. Strain and displacement values calculated by GPA show maximum values at the defect locations. There are possibly two phenomena contributing to such variations of the structure on the local level—twining and ordering. Perovskites such as LaCoO_3 are known to undergo a displacive phase transition from a paraelastic cubic perovskite (space group $Pm-3m$ stable at high temperature) to a ferroelastic rhombohedral perovskite (space group $R-3c$). The rhombohedral phase is

Figure 3. TEM micrographs and strain distribution calculated by geometrical phase analysis (GPA) of samples prepared with gelatine concentration of 0.0 g l^{-1} (row a), 1.5 g l^{-1} (row b), and 7.5 g l^{-1} (row c). Yellow arrows in the TEM images (column 1) point towards nanoparticles of secondary phases (Co_3O_4 and La_2O_3). HRTEM images (column 2) show atomic arrangements along [100] pseudocubic/[1-11] rhombohedral direction. Column 3 shows corresponding FFTs displaying superstructure reflections at $1/3$ and $2/3$ of the reciprocal unit cell (see yellow arrows). Strains ε_{xx} and ε_{xy} are plotted in Column 4 and 5, respectively.

formed by a compression along one of the the original cubic unit cell four body diagonals. Any combination of two of these four domain states can meet on pseudo cubic (100) planes to form (100) twins, alternatively they can meet on pseudo cubic (110) planes forming (110) twins.³⁶ The deformational twinning, however, cannot cause the additional ordering of the structure observed for the LaCoO_3 prepared without gelatine (Fig. 3).

Consequently, the samples prepared with 1.5 g l^{-1} of gelatine show much weaker superstructure ordering with irregularly spaced planar defects separating larger single-crystal domains dominating the local structure. In this arrangement one may also expect a formation of Ruddelsden-Popper (RP) faults creating double LaO layers.³⁷ Increasing the amount of gelatine in the reaction mixture leads to an intermediate behavior when the materials show features characteristic to both previously addressed types of local structure arrangement. It needs to be noted that the actual effect of the gelatine on the distribution of the defects is specific for La-Co-O system and cannot be easily transferred to chemically similar systems like, e.g. La-Ni-O.²¹ One can also suggest variability in defect ordering as the prevailing mechanism controlling the particle size of the prepared materials leading to significantly smaller particle size for the material synthesized with 1.5 g l^{-1} of gelatine. Further experiments would be, however, necessary to prove this effect conclusively.

The materials synthesized in the presence of higher amounts of gelatine feature a separation of the oxygen vacancies and ordered domains in the nanocrystals with both dominant structural features coexisting in the crystals. The materials prepared with high gelatine concentration, therefore, combine the behavior observed for materials prepared with no gelatine and with low concentration of gelatine. The oxygen vacancies tend to get arranged in the superstructures characteristic to perovskites prepared in the absence of gelatine. This vacancy ordering is demonstrated in the electron diffractograms obtained in FFT analysis of the HRTEM images of the materials prepared in the presence of high concentration of gelatine (note corresponding diffraction spots similar to those observed for materials prepared in absence of gelatine (see the third column of the row c of the Fig. 3). At the same time, the defects

observed in the rhombohedral phase prepared in absence of gelatine remain confined into continuous domains. The overall volume of these domains is, however, smaller than in the case of the materials synthesised in presence of small gelatine concentrations (see Fig. 3). In addition, these samples contain a small amount of secondary phases. The presence of Co_3O_4 and La_2O_3 is indicated by electron diffraction patterns (Fig. S8). Small nanoparticles about 10 nm in size attached to the surface of large LaCoO_3 particles show lattice spacing of 4.7 \AA corresponding to (111) d-spacing of Co_3O_4 , and their elemental composition determined by EDX further corroborates the presence of Co_3O_4 phase with significant amount of oxygen vacancies (Fig. S9).

Electrochemical activity.—The distribution of stacking faults as well as of oxygen vacancies has a profound effect on the catalytic behavior. The electrochemical activity of the materials prepared with the different contents of gelatine before and after exfoliation was initially assessed by cyclic voltammetry (Fig. 4 and it is presented on example of two limiting synthetic conditions—in absence of gelatine and in presence of high concentration of gelatine (7.5 g l^{-1}) in the reaction mixture. The electrochemical behavior of materials prepared with intermediate concentrations of gelatine are qualitatively similar.

Due to the rich redox chemistry of cobalt, the survey cyclic voltammetry was performed in a wide potential range between -0.5 V and 1.7 V vs RHE. Analysing the observed voltammograms, one needs to separate the behaviour encountered in the anodic scan from that recorded during the cathodic scan. The as-prepared materials (regardless of the gelatine content used in the synthesis) show the anodic branch of the voltammogram free of redox features typical for the redox behaviour of Co. Such behaviour can be expected given the perovskite nature of the prepared materials, which assumes that Co occupies octahedrally coordinated B site positions and is in a single oxidation state of III before the onset of the oxygen evolution at the anodic limit. The cathodic branch of the voltammogram is dominated by a wave-like broad cathodic signal, which appears in a wide interval between ca. 0.7 V and the onset of

Figure 4. CV curves of LaCoO_3 synthesized with 0.0 g l^{-1} and 7.5 g l^{-1} gelatine; where the effect of exfoliation (ink 2 – red curve) is compared with no exfoliation (ink 1 – black curve) in (a) potential range from -0.5 V to 1.7 V vs RHE and (b) potential window from 0.8 V to 1.7 V (zoomed CV of (a)) measured in 0.1 M KOH electrolyte at 10 mV s^{-1} scan rate.

hydrogen evolution. This cathodic signal, however, lacks a resolved anodic counterpart and represents most likely a reduction of the oxygen generated in situ at anodic potentials positive to 1.2 V vs RHE. The actual gelatine content has a complex effect on the electrochemical activity of the prepared materials. In general, the addition of gelatine into the reaction mixture leads to a decrease in the characteristic particle size (see Fig. 2b), resulting in an increase in the double layer capacitance. Aside from the increase of the capacitive current, the La-Co-O materials prepared in the presence of gelatine show an increase in the activity in both oxygen evolution as well as in oxygen reduction (see below).

The exfoliation of the prepared materials by adding the acetic acid into the catalyst ink leads to an increase in the observed currents (see Fig. 4). It needs to be noted that the voltammograms recorded on exfoliated materials reflect, in general, an increased electrode area resulting in higher capacitive currents. It is necessary to point out that the exfoliation leads to a qualitative difference in electrochemical behaviour immediately preceding the oxygen evolution. This qualitative change in the electrochemical behaviour manifests itself by a redox pair located at ca. 1.45 V vs RHE. While the anodic signal, to a great extent, overlaps with the onset of the oxygen

evolution current, the cathodic peak at 1.45 V vs RHE is rather well resolved in voltammograms taken on exfoliated samples. This reversible redox signal can be ascribed to a $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{4+}$ redox pair,³⁸ suggesting that the formation of Co^{4+} is prerequisite for efficient oxygen evolution. It also needs to be noted that the voltammograms recorded on exfoliated samples do not contain any signals attributable to $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$ charge transfer which should be characteristic for Co_3O_4 spinel contamination.³⁹

OER activity.—A specific role of the local structure and morphology directed by the gelatine addition projects also into the activity of the prepared materials in the oxygen evolution reaction (Fig. 5). The presence of gelatine during the synthesis has rather a complex effect on the OER activity of non-exfoliated materials. In general, the OER activity of the materials prepared without gelatine drops after adding gelatine into the reaction mixture. The activity of the gelatine affected La-Co-O materials generally improves with increasing concentration of gelatine. An exclusion from the rule represents the material prepared from a reaction mixture containing 1.5 g of gelatine per litre, which shows rather high activity in oxygen evolution reaction. Rather high activity of this material is most likely related to the smaller particle size of the nanocrystals and defect distribution in this material.

The exfoliation, as a rule, improves the oxygen evolving activity (Fig. 5b). Interestingly, a similar effect on the oxygen evolving activity is observed for materials prepared without gelatine and for materials prepared at high concentrations of gelatine (7.5 g l^{-1}). The exfoliation has a smaller effect on the behaviour of materials prepared from the mixture containing the low concentration of gelatine. In the particular case of the materials synthesized in the presence of 1.5 g l^{-1} of gelatine, one observes a decrease of the oxygen-evolving activity for exfoliated samples. The behaviour recorded in the oxygen evolution reaction clearly shows that the addition of the gelatine to the reaction mixture affects the resulting materials beyond mere faceting and particle size. Significant enhancement of the OER activity as encountered for gelatine free material and for materials prepared at high gelatine concentrations may be interpreted in terms of the specific surface area increase caused by exfoliation. The same effects are, on the other hand, significantly smaller in materials prepared at low to moderate gelatine concentrations. This trend can be ascribed to a difference in the local structure which shows a significant dependence on the gelatine present in the synthesis. The materials showing an enhancement of the OER activity usually feature local structure dominated by oxygen vacancies and their ordering, which become the starting point of the exfoliation process and determine the surface composition of the exfoliated surfaces. The materials tending to direct the strain to the domain boundaries, on the other hand, show a low tendency to exfoliation. The same trend is also reflected in the ratio of the OER activity of the LaCoO_3 with and without exfoliation (see Fig. 5c) which clearly shows that relative increase of the activity in oxygen evolution increases with increasing number and order of the oxygen vacancies. A relative drop in this ratio is experienced for the material synthesized with 7.5 g l^{-1} of gelatine can be ascribed to the preferential dissolution of the secondary phases which apparently show lower resistance towards exfoliating agent. At the same time one needs to stress that the surface chemistry of the exfoliated materials in inks may differ from non-exfoliated ones which may affect the resulting electrocatalytic activity.

ORR activity.—The effect of the exfoliation, however, goes beyond simple geometric arrangement which may appear to be the primary driver of the observed increase of OER activity. A complementary characterization of the catalytic behaviour of the prepared La-Co-O materials can be extracted from oxygen reduction characteristics as shown in Fig. 6. It needs to be noted that although some of the materials prepared at quite different conditions show a similarity in the response to exfoliating agent in OER (see Fig. 5), the effect of exfoliation on ORR clearly distinguishes the

Figure 5. (a) LSV curves of LaCoO₃ samples synthesized with different amounts of gelatine measured in RDE arrangement at a rotating speed of 1600 rpm at a scan rate of 5 mV s⁻¹ in 0.1 M KOH before adding the exfoliating agent (ink 1 - black curve) and after 1 hr of sonication with the addition of exfoliating agent in ink mixture (ink 2 - red curve) (b) Current density calculated at a potential of 1.7 V vs RHE of all synthesized LaCoO₃ samples without and with exfoliation. (c) A ratio of the OER activity with and without exfoliation of all synthesized LaCoO₃ samples.

synthetic conditions, namely the presence of the gelatine in the reaction mixture. It also needs to be stressed that to have unfettered information on the ORR mechanism no carbon additive was added to enhance electrical conductivity.⁴⁰

The exfoliation affects apparently both the overall activity as well as the selectivity of the ORR process. Comparing the behaviour of the material prepared without gelatine and material prepared at the highest gelatine concentration (7.5 g l⁻¹), which show qualitatively the same enhancement of the OER activity by exfoliation, one obtains significantly different behaviour in ORR (Figs. 6a and 6c). The exfoliation of the material synthesized in the absence of gelatine leads to a significant increase in the overall reduction activity (compare red and black disk currents plotted in Fig. 6a bottom), which is accompanied by a suppression of the hydrogen peroxide formation as attest suppressed ring currents (Fig. 6a). The material prepared in the presence of 7.5 g l⁻¹ of gelatine shows a much weaker response to exfoliation in oxygen reduction (Fig. 6c) as far as both overall activity and selectivity are concerned. The exfoliated material shows a comparable disk current as well formation of hydrogen peroxide as

before exfoliation. This behaviour suggests that the exfoliation is a rather complex process going beyond a simple increase of the specific surface area. This statement is further enhanced by the behaviour encountered for materials prepared in the presence of low concentrations of the gelatine, which show a moderate enhancement of the overall reduction activity accompanied by a significant decrease of the hydrogen peroxide formation (Fig. 6b).

Given the fact that the observed RRDE curves recorded during the ORR do not show a clear distinction between transport and kinetics-controlled regimes, the number of transferred electrons (*n*) becomes the key parameter in evaluating the performance of electrocatalysts.⁴¹ The number of electrons transferred (*n*) during ORR is shown in Fig. 6d and clearly depicts the effect of exfoliation. The *n* values on non-exfoliated materials are close to 3, signifying that the non-exfoliated materials show a similar tendency to reduce the oxygen to OH⁻ and to H₂O₂. It needs to be noted that the exfoliation leads to a selectivity shift towards OH⁻ formation as the *n* increases by 0.1 (materials synthesized at high gelatine concentration) to 0.6 (material prepared at the concentration of gelatine 1.5 g l⁻¹). In this light, the

Figure 6. RRDE curve response of LaCoO₃ with gelatine concentration of (a) 0.0 g l⁻¹ (b) 1.5 g l⁻¹ (c) 7.5 g l⁻¹ (black lines—without exfoliation, red lines—with exf.) (d) number of electrons transferred (*n*) during ORR on materials experiencing no exfoliation (open symbols) and experiencing 1 h of exfoliation (solid symbols).

material prepared without gelatine shows a moderate behaviour characterized by an increase of *n* by ca 0.4. It needs to be noted that the hydrogen peroxide formation on LaCoO₃ materials prepared by the spray-freeze freeze-drying approach is slightly higher than that reported in the literature.⁴²

Although it seems likely that this enhanced preference of two electron reduction as well its change to 4 electron reduction after exfoliation can be connected with a change of the prevailing mechanism of the oxygen reduction process^{43–46} the available experimental data do not provide a sufficient support to explain the observed trends conclusively and a dedicate study employing DFT modelling would be needed to elucidate the origin of the observed effects.

Conclusions

Summarizing the above outlined behaviour the spray-freeze freeze-drying synthesis in the presence of gelatine affects profoundly the reactivity and catalytic activity of the prepared materials. The addition of gelatine affects the prepared materials beyond directing the shape of the prepared materials. Most importantly, it directs the distribution of oxygen vacancies which show a great tendency for

ordering in La–Co–O phase prepared without gelatine. Gelatine addition initially tends to direct the defects into boundaries separating well ordered domains with low strain lattice. A presence of high concentrations of gelatine, on the other hand, supports both ordering of oxygen vacancies as well formation of domains within individual nanocrystals.

The presence of the ordered oxygen vacancies and their distribution generally affects the electrocatalytic behaviour of the prepared materials in oxygen electrocatalysis. The electrocatalytic activity of the materials featuring ordering of the oxygen vacancies in the volume in general improves OER activity in alkaline media. This trend even gets accentuated after exfoliation of the prepared materials. The exfoliation generally leads to a formation of new surface which manifests itself in enhanced signals of Co (III)/Co (IV) transition preceding the actual oxygen evolution. The increased presence of Co on the surface leads directly to an increase of the OER activity.

The exfoliation along oxygen vacancies and/or domain boundaries, however, affects the catalytic behaviour of the prepared La–Co–O phases on a more fundamental level as can be inferred from oxygen reduction behavior. The exfoliation in general leads to

significant change in the number of electrons involved in the oxygen reduction reaction. More profound change towards four-electron oxygen reduction encounters for materials prepared with low gelatine concentration, featuring a confinement of the available defects into domain boundaries indicates the role confined in the relatively stable domains in steering catalytic behaviour namely in oxygen reduction.

The engineering of the defects and their ordering can be used as an additional instrument in advanced oxide catalyst design.

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